

Habitat structure as an alternative explanation for body-size patterns in the deep sea

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Abstract. Patterns in body size are important to study as the size of an organism correlates with many biological traits of the organism. Changes in the size distribution of a community can be indicative of environmental change and/or anthropogenic impacts. What structures body size is, however, still poorly understood, with many factors proposed and shown to influence body size, including energy, which is likely a major driver. The deep sea is a good test bed to explore the relationship between body size and the availability of energy as it is an energy-poor system, and strong responses to energy changes are expected. Here, we test the increased packing hypothesis that states that the modal size class should increase with energy, while other size classes reduce in abundance, resulting in less variance in the distribution. This has been demonstrated to be the case in a system with discrete food resources, but here we test what happens when energy is not discretely distributed. Furthermore, we test for alternative explanations using habitat structure to explain patterns in body size. We find no support for the increased packing hypothesis for the two energy variables used, but we did find strong patterns with habitat structure. Only when habitat structure was included did we find a small effect of particulate organic carbon on the mean body size. It is likely that how energy is partitioned in an ecosystem influences its structuring effect; when energy is not distributed in a discrete way, this can obfuscate the relationship. Habitat structure influences how energy is distributed in a system, and studying body size in relation to both habitat structure and energy may further our understanding in what structures this aspect of benthic communities.

Key words: body size; deep sea; energy availability; habitat structure; polychaetes.

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INTRODUCTION

Patterns in body size are recognized as important integrative correlations of species and their traits. Many important relationships, including physiological rates, abundance, home ranges, trophic status, productivity, nutrient cycling, and species richness, relate with body size and are important in structuring communities (Hutchinson and MacArthur 1959, Peters 1983, Brown et al. 2004, Woodward et al. 2005). Many of these relationships can be predicted using species' metabolic rates and temperature, as outlined by

the metabolic theory of ecology (MTE) and highlight the influential role of energy in these processes (Brown et al. 2004). Studying body size is an important and useful tool to study animal–environment interactions; for example, changes in body-size distributions can result from ecological and/or anthropogenic disturbance (Allen et al. 1999, Mindel et al. 2018). However, what specifically structures body-size distributions in nature remains unclear. Many hypotheses have been formed, which can be grouped in different categories: energetic hypotheses (Brown et al. 1993, Kelt 1997), phylogenetic hypotheses (Gardezi

and da Silva 1999, Cassey and Blackburn 2004, Smith 2004), biogeographic hypotheses (Hubbell 1997, Marquet and Cofre 1999, Siemann and Brown 1999, Hoekstra and Fagan 1998, Silva et al. 2001), textural discontinuity hypotheses (Holling 1992, Ritchie and Olf 1999), and community interaction hypotheses (Hutchinson 1959, Oksanen et al. 1979, Stubblefield et al. 1993, Nummi et al. 2000). Often, these hypotheses address patterns at different spatial and temporal scales (Allen et al. 2006), meaning that they are not necessarily mutually exclusive.

Deep-sea body-size patterns and distributions have predominantly been studied in relation to energy. Global-scale patterns indicate that many faunal groups, but not bacteria, decrease in size with increasing depth (Rex et al. 2006), which is thought to be influenced by a decrease in food (chemical) availability. As energy is limited in the deep sea, it can be a strong factor controlling or influencing many aspects of deep-sea organisms, including abundance, biomass, life history, and species richness (Gage and Tyler 1991, Rex and Etter 2010, Woolley et al. 2016). McClain et al. (2012) demonstrated that deep-sea organisms' body-size patterns are concurrent with predictions from the MTE, indicating the importance of chemical and thermal energy in these patterns as well as the generality of the MTE across ecosystems. How energy may mechanistically influence body-size distributions is unclear, but there is some support for the increased packing hypothesis: In response to increases in energy, the modal size class increases in abundance and species richness, while the other size classes do not, resulting in decreased variance in the body-size distribution (McClain et al. 2018). This hypothesis has been tested for wood falls, a spatially discrete and unique food source in the deep sea, whereas most food sources in the deep sea are not discrete and isolated and mostly come in the form of a rain of organic matter (marine snow) from above. Furthermore, while energy is likely a very important structuring factor in the deep sea, it has not been able to explain all variations in patterns in body size observed in slope and abyssal habitats; other patterns, such as no relationship between depth and body size, increase in body size with increasing depth, or parabolic relationships between depth and body size have been found (Polloni et al. 1979, Rex et al. 1999,

Vanhove et al. 2004, McClain et al. 2005). These differences can be explained by regional effects, although other suggestions, such as taxonomic and sampling effects, may play a role too (McClain et al. 2006, van der Grient and Rogers 2015). One other candidate is habitat structure, which has been demonstrated to be influential in terrestrial and shallow-water studies in explaining body-size patterns (Schwinghamer 1981, Polo and Carrascal 1999, Fu et al. 2004, Gutierrez and Iribarne 2004, Pitmann et al. 2004, Stead et al. 2005). The role of habitat structure in deep-sea body-size patterns has been less explored, but it is reasonable to assume that in this system too habitat structure plays a role.

Here, we test the increased packing hypothesis using samples from a soft-sediment system. Energy in soft sediments is not isolated in space as are wood-fall samples. If energy is important in such a way that it does not matter whether the resource is isolated in space or not, and thus that an effect of energy on body size can be detected, then in this system too there should be support for the increased packing hypothesis. If, however, the isolation of energy does influence the effect of energy on body size, then an effect may not be detected. To determine support for the increased packing hypothesis, there should be no change in the mean and modality of community body size with increased energy availability, while the variance of the distribution should decrease, and kurtosis of the distribution should increase. Two different energy measures were used here to test the hypothesis: total carbon at the seafloor, which constituted available energy to the community at the time of sampling, and particulate organic carbon (POC) at the sea surface, which represented future energy availability. The reason why two different energy measures were used is because it remains unclear how deep-sea communities may respond to energy. Deep-sea communities can respond rapidly to changes in energy in the deep sea (Billet et al. 2010). The flux of carbon to the seafloor may vary because of seasonality, vertical transportation, lateral advection, resuspension, and transfer efficiency (Buesseler 2007, Dell'Anno et al. 2013). Also, quantities of carbon at the seafloor may not represent available energy as it has already been used, and thus represents a poor estimation of potential energy. It is therefore possible that total carbon at the seafloor may not be

an adequate measure of potential energy available to the benthos and may not correlate well with community patterns. POC, on the other hand, can be used to estimate how much may end up in the deep sea. While energy will decrease with increasing depth as a result of remineralization (Rex and Etter 1992, Rex et al. 1999, Buesseler 2007), and thus, POC is an overestimate of energy availability in itself, it can be used to predict the seafloor biomass (Wei 2010), thus showing POC to be a good predictor of energy availability at the seafloor.

Furthermore, to explore the effect of habitat structure in relation to energy availability, we tested whether and how different predictors of habitat structure and energy availability relate to body size. Both total carbon and POC were used again to represent energy availability for reasons outlined above. Studies from other systems have shown habitat structure is important in explaining body-size patterns (Restrepo et al. 1997, Allen et al. 1999, Havlicek and Carpenter 2001, Allen and Saunders 2002, Sendzimir et al. 2003, Gutierrez and Iribarne 2004, Fu et al. 2004, Polo and Carrascal 1999, Pitmann et al. 2004, Stead et al. 2005); especially at larger, regional spatial scales (Allen et al. 2006). Habitat structure can influence niche space, living space, and/or opportunities to exploit resources which in turn influence abundance, biomass, diversity, and body size (MacArthur and Wilson 1967, Holling 1992, Ritchie and Olff 1999). For example, greater habitat structure could mean that there are more micro-niches available to the community, thus increasing the abundance and richness of smaller species, although it may have additional influence on predators preying on these smaller species. The two variables representing habitat structure that were included were slope angle and sponge density. Seafloors can be characterized by terrain parameters, such as slope angle, and slope angle has been demonstrated to be a useful classifier for distinct habitat and fauna (Lundblad et al. 2006, Wilson et al. 2007, Jones and Brewer 2012). Slope angle is a useful proxy for correlated, but unmeasured, factors at the seafloor, including current regime, habitat heterogeneity, substratum type, sedimentation, and food availability (Jones et al. 2013). Sponges have been shown to have a structuring effect on biodiversity in deep-sea communities (Buhl-Mortensen et al. 2010, Hogg et al.

2010, Barrio-Frojan et al. 2012), and it is possible that they influence other attributes of the community too. For example, the loss of spicules increases habitat heterogeneity in soft sediments. This increased heterogeneity may result in an increase in smaller organisms if it provides increased living spaces for them, either by providing hiding places, or increased surface areas, or potentially as it influences food availability. If there was an effect of sponge density, then more smaller organisms would be expected.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Biological data

This study was undertaken on 30 box-core samples, constituting 2844 polychaete individual organisms in total. The samples were part of a larger sampling program that was undertaken as part of the North Atlantic Fisheries Organization PotEntial VulneRable Marine Ecosystems—Impacts of Deep-sea Fisheries (NEREIDA) project during cruises in 2009 (May–August) and 2010 (June–August) on board of the *Miguel Oliver*. Samples were located around the Flemish Cap, the Flemish Pass, and Grand Banks east and southeast of Newfoundland, Canada (Fig. 1). The latitude and longitude for each box-core sample were recorded at the time of sampling. To ensure a large spatial area was covered as well as minimizing potential spatial heterogeneity, a random-stratified approach was used by splitting the Flemish Pass, Flemish Cap, and Grand Banks sampling area into three areas based on latitude. In each of the three areas, 10 samples were randomly selected to be used for the body-size analyses. Sampling depth ranged between 580 and 1890 m depth. The biological samples were taken from the top 5 cm of the box-core sample and sieved at 1 mm sieve mesh size. The polychaete data were sorted to family level under a microscope and photographed for size measurements. Polychaetes are macrofaunal organisms that are numerically dominant in the macrofaunal size class in deep-sea benthic soft-sediment ecosystems. Most of the fragile worms were damaged during the sampling and sorting process, a common problem in deep-sea research. Methods have been developed to study polychaete body size in different ways rather than using the standard length or biomass

Fig. 1. Sample locations (red circles) located around the Flemish Cap, down the slopes of the Flemish Pass, and southern slopes of the Grand Banks. Blue shading indicates bathymetry variation, with darker blue representing deeper waters (>200 m).

approaches. For example, the width of the first chaetiger (segment) has been shown to correlate with body length and thus can be used as a proxy for body size (Paterson et al. 2006). The width of the first chaetiger (mm) was measured here for each photographed specimen using ImageJ V1.49. Each polychaete was measured three times, and the average of the measurements was used as sampling unit per polychaete taken to minimize measurement bias.

Environmental data

Multibeam surveys collected box-core sample depth and seafloor data to estimate slope angle, which was modeled in ArcGis10.1. Sponge distribution was modeled from previous trawl data following Kenchington et al. (2014), and data on sponge density (kg/km^2) per box-core location were extracted from this. Satellite data (MODIS AQUA) were used to extract data at box-core locations for POC (mg/m^3) at the sea surface for the years 2008–2010. Carbon content measurements were obtained from the box-core samples, and from that, total carbon (%) was calculated (Weitzman et al. 2014). These environmental

variables were selected as proxies for habitat structure (slope angle, sponge density) and (chemical) energy (POC and total carbon) for further analyses.

Data analysis

The average \log_{10} -transformed width per family per box core was determined and used to create a family–body size distribution. We calculated the average, standard deviation, kurtosis, and mode as part of different descriptors of the body-size distribution. We tested each feature against both energy variables separately. Kurtosis was estimated using the kurtosis function in the *psych* package in R, using the type 3 estimate (Revelle 2015). The number of modes was estimated based on the hierarchical clustering of Gaussian mixture models created using the *mclust* package in R Studio and Bayesian information criterion (Scrucca et al. 2016, R Core Team 2017). All models, except those related to the number of modes, were modeled using linear regression methods. Poisson generalized linear models were used to study the effects of the energy predictors on the number of modes. The

full models included an interaction with area, which was used as a blocking factor in all models. We only retained significant relationships in the model as well as the blocking factor. The slopes of the relationships were used to determine whether there was support for the increased packaging hypothesis.

To delineate the effects of energy and habitat structure together, a polynomial regression model was fitted to the average transformed body size. Two variables for both energy and habitat structure were included, as well as area as a blocking factor. Collinearity was not present between the explanatory variables. The full model was fitted as $\text{width} \sim \text{POC} \times \text{total carbon} \times \text{slope} \times \text{angle} \times \text{slope} \times \text{angle}^2 \times \text{sponge density} + \text{area}$. A second-order polynomial for slope angle was included as it is expected that organisms do not respond in a linear way to the increase in slope angle. Different seabed facies are associated with different slope angles, which in turn can represent different levels of habitat heterogeneity (Jones et al. 2013). It is likely that different functional groups respond to these unmeasured seabed factors and thereby show differences in community structure across the slope gradient. It is possible that both steep and flat slopes have a lack of habitat heterogeneity, reflected in the community that occurs in the habitats. For example, steep slopes may result in habitats that are inaccessible for many organisms (e.g., larger mobile benthic organisms may not be able to live on steep slopes, or as easily as smaller organisms) thereby repressing body sizes. Intermediate slope angles, on the other hand, may provide more habitat heterogeneity and thus niches, which may be reflected in body size. Both width and sponge density were log-transformed to meet model assumptions. Area was included as a blocking factor. The drop1 function was used to select and optimize the final model as well as summary outputs and Akaike information criterion. Analyses and figures were performed and created using the R packages dplyr, ggplot2, and gridExtra (Wickham 2016, Auguie 2017, Wickham et al. 2018).

RESULTS

A frequency distribution of all samples together demonstrated a normally distributed

family–body size distribution along the size classes (Fig. 2; Shapiro-Wilk $W = 0.889$, $P = 0.2312$), with a mean body size of $0.625 \log_{10}$ width units. No interactions between area and POC, or between area and total carbon were found for all body-size descriptors relationships (area \times POC mean $F_{2,24} = 0.13$, $P = 0.88$; standard deviation $F_{2,24} = 0.68$, $P = 0.52$; kurtosis $F_{2,24} = 0.08$, $P = 0.92$; mode $X_2^2 = 1.02$, $P = 0.6$; area \times total carbon mean $F_{2,24} = 1.00$, $P = 0.38$, standard deviation $F_{2,24} = 1.69$, $P = 0.21$; kurtosis $F_{2,24} = 0.86$, $P = 0.43$; mode $X_2^2 = 4.69$, $P = 0.10$), and models were refitted as additive models. None of the body-size descriptors showed significant relationships with POC, indicating no support for the increased packaging hypothesis (Fig. 3; mean -0.002 ± 0.002 , $F_{1,24} = 0.06$, $P = 0.81$; standard deviation 0.0003 ± 0.0008 , $F_{1,24} = 0.09$, $P = 0.77$; kurtosis -0.009 ± 0.013 , $F_{1,24} = 0.08$, $P = 0.78$; mode 0.001 ± 0.011 , $X_1^2 = 0.008$, $P = 0.93$). While there was some variety between the body-size descriptors and total carbon (average body size, standard deviation, and mode were positively correlated with total carbon, while kurtosis was negatively correlated), none of these relationships were significant (Fig. 4; mean -0.009 ± 0.019 , $F_{1,24} = 1.77$, $P = 0.20$; standard deviation 0.0009 ± 0.0009 , $F_{1,24} = 0.03$, $P = 0.87$; kurtosis -0.158 ± 0.138 , $F_{1,24} = 2.79$, $P = 0.11$; mode 0.304 ± 0.130 , $X_1^2 = 2.83$, $P = 0.09$). Area also did not significantly correlate with any of the body-size descriptors (POC mean $F_{2,26} = 2.79$, $P = 0.08$; standard deviation $F_{2,26} = 1.54$, $P = 0.23$; kurtosis $F_{2,26} = 1.56$, $P = 0.23$; mode $X_2^2 = 0.74$, $P = 0.69$; total carbon mean $F_{2,26} = 0.83$, $P = 0.45$; standard deviation $F_{2,26} = 1.48$, $P = 0.25$;

Fig. 2. The family–body size distribution based on \log_{10} size classes in a soft-sediment polychaete community.

Fig. 3. Body-size distribution descriptors in relation to energy availability (particulate organic carbon; POC), with (A) mean, (B) standard deviation, (C) kurtosis, and (D) number of modes of the distribution. The blue line represents the best fit of the linear regressions, and shaded areas represent the 95% confidence interval.

kurtosis $F_{2,26} = 0.66$, $P = 0.53$, mode $X^2_2 = 3.37$, $P = 0.19$).

Investigating the average body size using the two energy and habitat structure variables shows different patterns. The final model contained none of the interactions and was purely additive. Total carbon was dropped from the model too as it was not significant ($F = 0.0022$, $P = 0.96$). All other relationships were maintained in the model. There was a linear negative relationship between mean body size and POC (-0.003 ± 0.001 , $F = 4.41$, $P = 0.047$); the P -value is close to the significance cutoff, and as backward selection is used, this relationship should be interpreted with caution. Both habitat structure variables (sponge density and slope angle) had significant relationships with body size. There was a polynomial relationship between slope angle and body size (Fig. 5; first-order: 0.14 ± 0.09 ; second-order: $-0.24^2 \pm 0.08$; whole relationship for slope angle: $F = 5.19$, $P = 0.014$), and a negative linear relationship between sponge density and body size (Fig. 6; -0.056 ± 0.02 , $t = -3.26$, $P = 0.003$). Area was included as a blocking factor, and while it was not significant ($P = 0.30$), it was maintained in the model.

DISCUSSION

Body-size patterns in the deep sea have been related predominantly to energetic explanations. Here, we demonstrate a case where no relationship between (chemical) energy alone and body size was found, but instead habitat structure (slope angle and sponge density) was better in describing body-size patterns. Only in combination with habitat structure did we find an effect of energy on body size. Energy is known to play an important role in structuring deep-sea communities, but further understanding can be gained when both energy and habitat structure are used in the study of body size.

The models presented here showed no support for the increased packaging hypothesis, in contrast to a previously studied wood-fall community (McClain et al. 2018). Energy has been shown to be a dominant factor in many deep-sea patterns, such as abundance, biomass, and diversity (Rex and Etter 2010, Woolley et al. 2016), as well as previous body-size studies (Rex et al. 2006, McClain et al. 2012, 2018). One obvious difference between this study and the wood-fall study is the nature of the chemical energy: Wood

Fig. 4. Body-size distribution descriptors in relation to energy availability (total carbon), with (A) mean, (B) standard deviation, (C) kurtosis, and (D) number of modes of the distribution. The blue line represents the best fit of the linear regressions, and shaded areas represent the 95% confidence interval.

falls are discrete energy patches, while both POC at the sea surface and total carbon at the seafloor are not. The isolation of the wood-fall resources is reflected in an endemic community which shares little overlap with the background community, and its whole community is sampled when a food wall is sampled (Voight 2007, McClain and Barry 2014, McClain et al. 2016). In contrast, samples from a soft-sediment are not as isolated in terms of food resources, and samples taken from these systems may not capture the whole community present, which may bias the relationship. For example, rare or large mobile groups may be undersampled in box cores, although it is thought that local diversity represents a regional species pool (Carney 1997, Lamshead and Boucher 2003, Rex and Etter 2010). If rare groups are different in size, then the size distribution is misrepresented. The energy variables used themselves are not isolated either, which may change or affect the mechanism underlying the relationship between energy and body size. For example, the lack of isolation can mean that the energy measures are not accurate representations of energy availability in the system. Many of the mobile

macrofaunal organisms may forage over a larger area than represented by the box-core sampling area, thereby distorting the relationship. Furthermore, wood falls from McClain et al. (2018) were homogeneous food patches, while, for example, the total carbon available at the sediment is unlikely to be homogenous as a result of the different sources it may come from (e.g., fecal pellets, dead organisms, mucus, larvacean houses, phytoplankton exoskeletons) and is unlikely to be homogeneously distributed across the seafloor as a result of seafloor morphology and currents (Silver et al. 1978, Robison et al. 2005, Buesseler 2007, Honjo et al. 2008). It is possible that this heterogeneity modifies the relationship. The importance of heterogeneity also plays a role in wood falls; for example, when there is heterogeneity in species of wood and what part of the tree is present, different communities are assembled on the food resource (Judge and Barry 2016). While the isolation of wood falls makes for excellent study systems, most other systems are not so isolated, and understanding the interplay between this lack of isolation and body-size relationships will be important in explaining patterns across systems.

Fig. 5. The parabolic relationship between slope ($^{\circ}$) and average polychaete body size (mm). The blue line represents the best fit of the polynomial regression, and shaded areas represent the 95% confidence interval.

The data investigating body-size distribution descriptors would seem to support the size invariance hypothesis, which states that descriptors do not change with increased energy as abundance, and species richness in proportion to abundance, in each size class increases. While there were some abundance changes in each size class, it was not consistent for each size class or similar between the two energy measures (results not shown), warranting further investigation. As stated earlier, the two energy variables were used as it is unclear which is the better predictor in terms of energy availability. Total carbon represents energy that was available at that moment, but may be a poor estimator of what was available, while POC does represent the potential of energy to be available (in a way, similar to knowing the size of the log before the experiment), and POC has been shown to predict seafloor biomass well (Smith et al. 2006, Johnson et al. 2007, Wei 2010) but there is a time lag until it becomes available for the seafloor community. This time lag may be important to incorporate as deep-sea communities may be able to respond rapidly to food influx, which may change the community composition (e.g., by changing the structure of

Fig. 6. The relationship between sponge density (kg/km^2) and average polychaete body size (mm). The correlation was negative and linear. There was an outlier, but this did not affect the relationship in terms of significance and direction. Both variables were log-transformed.

age cohorts) although stability in the carbon flux may be likewise important (Graf 1989, Ruhl and Smith 2004, Corliss et al. 2009, Billet et al. 2010). While investigating the energy measures alone suggested there was no influence of energy on body size, in combination with the habitat structure variables, POC was found to potentially have a small effect on body size, suggesting an interplay between these different factors in structuring body size in the community.

Habitat structure, especially in soft-sediment systems as studied here, may have unrecognized influence on body-size patterns in the deep sea. Habitat structure has been shown to influence body-size patterns in other systems (Polo and Carrascal 1999, Fu et al. 2004, Gutierrez and Iribarne 2004), and in particle size, diversity as a measure of habitat structure in shallow waters may influence body size (Schwinghamer 1981, Warwick 1984, Raffaelli et al. 2000, although see Leaper et al. 2001). Thus, it is not unconceivable that the same mechanisms apply to deep-sea benthic communities. In the study area, additional structure, in and on the sediments, can be formed by sponges, which in turn can influence

the community. For example, sponges can affect the sediment by forming spicule mats of lost and broken spicules. The presence of such mats has been observed in this area before (Barrio-Frojan et al. 2012). These mats may create or increase heterogeneity and structure in otherwise potentially homogeneous sediments. The influence on habitat by the presence of sponges and their lost body parts has been recognized in previous studies focusing on invertebrate diversity, even at phylum level (Bett and Rice 1992, Buhl-Mortensen et al. 2010, Hogg et al. 2010, Barrio-Frojan et al. 2012). The mechanism by which the effect of this complexity results in smaller body sizes is not known. The sponge spicules may increase the availability of micro-niches, which then should result in an increase in smaller organisms (Bell 2008). It is possible that the presence of spicules results in a size selectivity, meaning that the shape or arrangement of habitat space selects for smaller organisms (Hacker and Steneck 1990). It is also possible that the presence of sponges and their spicules modify the living space to such a point that it facilitates the presence of smaller individuals (Hastings et al. 2007). There is a clear pattern for a decrease in body size with increasing sponge density in this study, although there was no relationship between abundance and sponge density (results not shown), suggesting it is possibly not the availability of micro-niches that result in a decrease in body size, but instead there may be a selection effect. However, as the sponge data are modeled and not, for example, sponge spicules collected at the box-core level, the mechanism behind the size reduction cannot be deduced.

Slope angle showed a parabolic relationship with body size. As stated before, organisms are unlikely to respond directly to slope angle, but instead slope angle can be used as a proxy for correlated but unmeasured physical factors of the seabed (representing habitat heterogeneity) to which the benthic organisms respond. Flat areas are, for example, inhabited by a different community compared to steep areas, highlighting that slope angle can be a useful proxy to discriminate between communities (Lundblad et al. 2006, Schlacher et al. 2007). Slope angle can be a proxy for other ecological variables associated with this habitat feature, including habitat heterogeneity, current regimes, substratum type, food

availability, and sedimentation (Jones et al. 2013). The gradient of a slope may be more favorable for some functional groups than others. For example, Jones et al. (2013) found that suspension feeders were more common on the steepest slopes, while deposit feeders occurred on flat slopes. However, when all organisms were taken together, the highest number of organisms occurred on the intermediate slope angles. Slope angle and sponge density were not correlated in this study, although previous studies have shown that slope angle is important in explaining the distribution of sponges in the Flemish and Grand Banks area (Knudby et al. 2013). Slope angle can influence the formation of internal waves, which are important in (global) ocean mixing, resulting in increased transport rate of sediment to greater depths, and sponges tend to occur in areas where internal waves are formed (Rudnick 2003, Garrett and Kunze 2007). Thus, slope angle, as a proxy, can potentially play an important role in explaining what structures communities, and this variable may be especially important in areas with variable habitat structure such as here, or areas such as canyons and seamounts (Jones et al. 2013).

Several studies have called for the recognition and inclusion of multiple factors in describing and explaining body-size patterns in nature (Robson et al. 2005, Stead et al. 2005), and the results here support this notion. Energy can predict many important biological patterns, from the individual to species diversity, but may act predominantly over large spatial and/or temporal scales (Brown et al. 2004, Allen et al. 2006). Hypotheses that focus on the effect of habitat structure, such as the textural discontinuity hypothesis, first described by Holling (1992), tend to focus on smaller spatial scales—regional instead of continental, and/or smaller time scales—ecological rather than geological (Allen et al. 2006). This suggests that habitat structure plays a role in structuring communities through the lens of the slower and larger acting processes (Allen et al. 2006). In order to consider current biological patterns, an understanding of how these different processes act on a particular community is needed to discern the mechanism behind it, as well as explain changes that may occur. How habitat structure and energy may be combined is unclear, but it is recognized that energy is not evenly distributed through a habitat, or

necessarily perceived in the same way by organisms of different sizes, which potentially may explain differences in body-size patterns. The discontinuous nature of environments influences the distribution of energy; this discontinuity can often be described in a fractal-like manner (Holling 1992, Enquist et al. 1999, Ritchie and Olff 1999, Lovegrove and Haines 2004). Fractal structures have been shown to influence how energy and material flow in organisms, as well as explain how different ecological relationships between organisms and their environment relate to scale, for example, by scaling resource use by species, showing that, like energetic relationships, there is potential for generality in the use of fractals across scales of biological organization (West et al. 1997, Enquist et al. 1999, Ritchie and Olff 1999, Brown et al. 2004, Halley et al. 2004).

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